

HOW TO CREATE AND USE ELECTRONIC EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS 'PROGRAMMING ALGORITHMIC THINKING

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Annotation. This article provides suggestions and recommendations for creating and using an e-learning resource to develop students' algorithmic and logical thinking in programming in the C ++ Builder programming environment.

Key words: C++ Builder, programming, algorithmic thinking, logical, educational e-resources.

Ushbu maqolada C++ Builder dasturlash muhitida talabalarning dasturlashga oid algoritmik hamda mantiqiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishga mo'ljallangan elektron ta'lim resursi yaratish va undan foydalanish bo'yicha taklif va tavsiyalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: C++ Builder, dasturlash, algoritmik fikrlash, mantiqiy fikrlash, elektron ta'lim resursi.

Аннотация. В этой статье представлены предложения и рекомендации по созданию и использованию электронных ресурсов обучения, предназначенного для развития алгоритмического и логического мышления учащихся о программировании в среде программирования C ++ Builder.

Ключевые слова: C ++ Builder, программирование, алгоритмическое мышление, логическое мышление, электронный учебный ресурс.

Introduction . Nowadays further development of methodology of algorithmic thinking on programming as well as improvement of computer science and informational technologies are becoming one of the modern issue of our modern life in higher education institutions [1, 2, 4].

The solution to these problems is to develop an alternative algorithm for teaching programming technologies in accordance with the methodological features of pedagogical research for the training of future specialists in the field of computer science. This requires, first of all, the analysis of the literature in the field and the analysis of research in this area.

Literature review. Theory, methodology of introduction of information and communication technologies in the system of uninterrupted education, methods of creation and use of electronic educational resources, problems of application of distance learning technologies, improvement of methods of teaching computer science have been studied by scientists such as Belova A.A., Abdukadirov, F.M., Zakirova, G.A., Rasulova, N.M., Babakhodjayeva, K.R., Mamadaliyev, V.T., Jurayev, J.K., Nurbekova, F.V., Shkarban, I.V., Morozova, T.V., Atyaskina, Y.V., Chernobay.

However, their research has not been sufficiently researched to improve the methodology of programming, in particular the development of students' algorithmic and logical thinking in programming.

At the same time, although N.A. Otakhanov's research on object-oriented programming languages and M.R. Fayzieva's research on web-based programming teaching methods did not pay enough attention to the development of students' algorithmic thinking about programming. Therefore, this research is relevant for today's education system.

One of the solutions to this problem is to analyze the work of researchers on the creation of didactic tools, interactive methods, in particular, the creation of e-learning resources and their use in the educational process, which develop students' algorithmic thinking about programming.

In this regard, the research of GA Rasulova identified pedagogical and psychological requirements for the structure and content of multimedia e-

textbooks, and developed criteria and indicators for evaluating the effectiveness of the use of multimedia e-textbooks [3].

Interactivity of teaching on the basis of pedagogical and psychological requirements, such as the integration of teaching materials of different levels of complexity with ergonomic description of the structure and content of such multimedia e-textbooks, a high level of visualization, the reflection of a set of variable tasks; assumed that aspects of optimality would have didactic productivity.

At the same time, F.V.Shkarban emphasizes the need to develop targeted, meaningful and procedural components of the methodology of teaching the basics of object-oriented programming in the study using visual learning environments [4].

In his research, he suggested that it would be useful to increase the effectiveness of object-oriented programming teaching methods using visual learning environments.

In the research of NMBabakhodjayeva developed an algorithm for the design of algorithmic, logical thinking skills of students in the theory of algorithms on an entropic approach to the formation of algorithmic, logical thinking skills and justified the possibility of development through assignments. Based on the development of a software package for the theory of algorithms, the researcher proved the effectiveness of education [5].

K.R. Mamadaliyev's research has improved the principles of creating informative content that provides reproductive, productive, creative levels of critical thinking, independent search for information, the formation of analytical competencies in students, the mechanisms of creating modernized textbooks and electronic textbooks [6].

I.V Morozova's research has developed requirements for the formation of competencies of future teachers of computer science in the design of e-learning

resources. It has developed a mechanism for the formation of professional competencies of future computer science teachers [7].

At the same time, the scientific research of T.V Atyaskina provided a set of necessary and sufficient organizational and pedagogical conditions for the successful formation of self-education skills of future programmers using electronic resources. Her research explores the possibilities of electronic resources that can effectively develop the self-education skills of future technicians and programmers [8].

According to the analysis of the work of the above-mentioned researchers and scholars, in developing students' algorithmic thinking about programming, it is first necessary to develop a methodology for creating and using e-learning resources related to programming.

Therefore, didactic, methodological, psychological, technical, aesthetic, ergonomic requirements should be taken into account when creating e-learning resources [9]. These requirements play a key role in increasing the efficiency of e-learning resources.

Research methodology. When creating e-learning resources, it is advisable to use the C ++ Builder programming environment. Therefore, using the C ++ Builder XE3 programming environment, an e-learning resource was developed to develop students 'algorithmic thinking about programming (Figure 1).

1-figure. Title page of the app.

This e-learning resource includes programs that develop students' algorithmic thinking about programming, as well as program code for these programs in C ++, Java and Python. In addition, questions and assignments of varying complexity (reproductive, productive, partially exploratory and creative) are combined.

Sample program codes are divided into linear, branching, iterative, functions, arrays, strings, and file handling sections. The programs in each section are listed in ascending order. For example, the Line Programs section window looks like this:

2-figure. Linear Applications section window.

The above window can be conditionally divided into two parts. 1. The task window on the left side of the window. 2. On the right is a window that describes the program code in C ++, Java and Python programming languages.

This view applies to each section, where the user cannot edit items that describe the terms of the assignment and the program code. But the possibility of copying has been created.

Also included are questions of varying difficulty for each section. Once the questions window is entered only the section with reproductive level is activated. One allowed to the second level after completing the first one.

At each stage, the questions are sorted by level of difficulty. The user can move on to the next question only if they answer the first question correctly. Here is an example of a question from this set of questions (3-figure):

3-figure. Reproductive level questions window.

Analysis and results. The success of the pedagogical experiments carried out in the process of conducting experimental work aimed at developing students' algorithmic thinking in programming shows the need to take into account its organizational and pedagogical aspects in this process. Therefore, special attention was paid to these aspects. Experimental work was carried out in 2020 among students studying at the Navoi State Pedagogical Institute in the field of "Methods of teaching computer science."

A total of 64 students were involved in the experiment and control groups. The experiments were conducted in three stages: emphatic; shaper; closing. During the highlighting phase of the experiment, students were interviewed and observed about the key features of programming languages.

At the formative stage, based on the proposed e-learning resource, the experimental group was trained and the following criteria were developed to assess the effectiveness of students' learning: motivational; cognitive; technological; creative.

In the final stage, a mathematical-statistical analysis based on the Student-Fisher criterion was performed in order to check the reliability of the results of the students in the experimental and control groups.

Using this criterion, formulas were used to determine the appropriate mean

values for the samples, scattering coefficients $\bar{X} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^4 n_i X_i$, $D_n = \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{n_i (x_i - \bar{X})^2}{n-1}$,

standard deviations $\tau_n = \sqrt{D_n}$, variances, $\delta_n = \frac{\tau_n}{X}$, reliable deviations of the

estimates $\Delta_n = t_{kh} \cdot \frac{D_n}{\sqrt{n}}$, $P = \frac{\bar{X}}{3} \cdot 100\% - \frac{\bar{Y}}{3} \cdot 100\%$ and mastering rates. The

calculation showed that the average mastering rate of the experimental group was higher than that of the control group, ie by 9%.

Conclusions and suggestions. To sum up, the development of students' algorithmic thinking about programming is of great importance today in the field of information technology. Because it requires the development of effective applications for the management of the entire industry, the implementation of electronic payments, the calculation of mathematical and economic problems, the development of software products for computers and mobile devices, and the exchange of data remotely. This can be done through programming languages. Therefore, in order to develop students' algorithmic thinking about programming in higher education institutions, it is important to first improve science programs and create a new generation of textbooks. At the same time, it is necessary to improve the system of organizing students' independent study. This will require students to be given practical assignments focused on creative thinking and the development of e-learning resources that will help them solve them.

Therefore, we recommend using the e-learning resource mentioned above to develop students' algorithmic thinking about programming. This e-learning resource encourages students to work independently and think critically. As a result, the formation of students' competencies can be achieved.

From the above statistical analysis, it can be concluded that the development of algorithmic thinking of students in higher education institutions in the

development of programming is the basis for the popularization of the proposed e-learning resource.

The proposed e-learning resource will help students to spend their free time meaningfully, to acquire knowledge independently, to increase their programming competence, and to develop algorithmic thinking.

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